

Innovative processing technologies for bio-based foamed thermoplastics

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Manufacturing technologies for bio-based materials

D7.1 First workshop for value chain definition

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
b-bTPs	bio-based thermoplastics
FIM	Foam Injection Moulding
CA	Consortium Agreement
GA	Grant Agreement
GenA	General Assembly
EAB	External Advisory Board
EAd	Ethics Advisor
EC	European Commission
ESLM	External Stakeholder Liaison Manager
IM	Innovation Manager
PDEC	Place for Dissemination and Exploitation
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leade

1. Executive Summary

WP7 aims to set up a VITAL "learning Factory" to ensure efficient data management, implement and measure the Sex and Gender dimension, develop PDEC with a clear activity roadmap, and establish a sustainable value chain. The last objective belongs to subtask 7.1.1 "Value chain definition"; where this deliverable is framed.

During the first months of the project, subtask 7.1.1's activities have been focused on the conceptualisation and creation of a methodology for the definition of VITAL's value chains throughout the different workshops that will take place. Furthermore, the first workshop was prepared and conducted during VITAL's first physical meeting (Helsinki, 28-29 September 2022).

This way, this deliverable contains a detailed description of the aforementioned methodology as well as an analysis of the main outcomes achieved after the consecution of this first seminar, mainly focused on the initial definition of the value chains. Thus, this document will be the first iteration of a series of workshops and a final report about VITAL's value chains.

It is worth mentioning that the initial due date for this deliverable was M1 (June 2022). Nevertheless, it was agreed to delay it to M4 (September 2022).

2. Introduction

VITAL aims to develop innovative processing solutions for the foamed thermoplastic industry by the adoption of b-bTPs as material for the three processing value chains: 3D foam printing, FIM and Bead foaming. The adoption of this material will help the transition of this industry to a more sustainable and circular economy.

Nevertheless, the three value chains must be defined within a circular economy context. To such an end, a series of workshops have been scheduled in order to collect, discuss and process relevant data from partnership, being the present document the results summary from the first workshop.

As mentioned above, this first workshop has been focused on the definition of the three value chains to be developed in VITAL project. Accordingly, a description of what a value chain is can be found in **Section 3**. Also, in the same section, a brief introduction of the three-value chain is made (3D printing, FIM and bean foaming). Since VITAL project not only focuses on the innovation of technology but also changes the foamed thermoplastic industry to a sustainable circular economy, the methodology chosen for the value chain's definition must consider its cyclability. Therefore, the present and future workshops will follow a circular business model design guide that is explained in **Section 4**. This guide is made of four steps that help to see how the chain can be looped while simultaneously creating value and exploiting it. The results and conclusions of this first workshop are in **Section 5**.

3. Value Chains

The value chain describes the activities needed to create a product or service. It comprises every step that involves bringing a product from conception to distribution, including raw materials recollection, manufacturing, technological development, etc.

VITAL is focused on the innovation of three process value chains inside the foamed thermoplastic processing value chains to develop innovative processing solutions to b-bTPs, which are:

- Foam Injection Moulding (FIM).
- Bead foaming of b-bTPs.
- 3D b-bTPs foam printing.

A short description of each value chain can be found below.

3.1 Foam Injection Moulding (FIM)

The FIM process consists of a granulated thermoplastic that is blended with a blowing agent, which expands the material, and this blend is injected into a mould. For this kind of process, significant work has been undertaken on the use of supercritical fluid. Otherwise, biopolymers processing variables and characterisation information are still scarce, reducing the implementation of b-bTPs in this value chain.

VITAL aim is an FIM processing approach based on a Digital Twin with virtual AI control, at same time a database of foamed b-bTPs parameters will be created.

3.2 Bead foaming of b-bTPs

Bead foaming produces small beads that can be moulded into complex parts by welding the beads, usually with steam. This method is used for polypropylene and polystyrene.

However, b-bTPs show problems with the use of steam due to hydrolysis-sensibility that causes degradation.

VITAL aims to create a bead foaming process for b-bTPs based on radio frequency. The development of radio frequency moulding technology will increase the use of b-bTPs into the bead foaming process because it removes steam and reduces hydrolysis while reducing energy usage.

3.3 3D b-bTPs foam printing

3D printing is the construction of a three-dimensional object from a digital 3D model without needing a pre-existing mould. Those objects could be made of steel or polymers, and there is a different process of 3D printing. The Fused deposition modelling uses filaments of thermoplastic material and is the most common 3D printing process in 2022.

The production of 3D foam printing using b-bTPs as raw materials are not developed, so VITAL aims to have achieved a globally unique 3D printing process which uses granulate feedstock and produce foams of different densities

4. Workshop methodology

One of VITAL's objectives is to help transform the foam thermoplastics' linear economy industry into a circular economy industry. This will be made by the implementation of innovative processing solution for foamed b-bTPs. Achieving this objective requires a methodology that not just defines the value chain but also allows to see circular business opportunities.

During the development of the workshop, a Circular business model design guide will be followed. As introduced before, this guide is composed of four steps. Within each workshop, one of these steps will be developed, however the previous steps will be checked to update any new project information. Additionally, it will be required some work outside the workshops from all the partners in order to acquire critical and valuable information. For this end, collaborative online applications will be used.

4.1 Circular business model design guide

The guide was developed by Ellen MacArthur Foundation in collaboration with PA Consulting and Exeter Business School, to identify circular opportunities and design business models that could create value chains

For the correct size the circular economy opportunity, the guide establishes that four steps are necessary:

1. Where to play
2. How to win
3. How to operate
4. How to profit

4.1.1 Where to play

In this step, the aim is to identify circular business opportunities. This stage is divided into three parts, described below:

- a) Map existing value flow.
This part involves identifying the flow of value of the considered system or value chain, taking into account which value can be managed or controlled by the business and which not.
For this project, the value chains to study are those considered in **Section 3**
- b) Consider lost value and value at risk.
From the map created in section 1A, the lost value in the system is identified, and future changes in the value chain that could be a risk are considered.
- c) Identify circular value opportunities.
Taking all the information from 1A and 1B, identify ways of creating and/or closing to recover lost value, maximising the existing value.

4.1.2 How to win

This step identifies how value could be created for the customers and key partners. This step is divided into two parts:

- a) Identify customers and key partners.
From step 1C, the best ideas are recollected. From each concept, a list of key partners or customers needed to make the idea happen is completed, also each partner is classified on how critical their collaboration is in the success of the idea (High, Medium, or Low)
- b) Define mutually beneficial circular value propositions.
The linear economy models are based on exchanging money for a product or service. Furthermore, in the circular economy, there is a two-way partnership where the costs incurred are outweighed by the benefits each party receives in relation to their needs.

Therefore, it is necessary to establish for each partner or customer considered in 2A their needs and develop the offer.

4.1.3 *How to operate*

The critical activity steps to develop the idea and the capabilities needed for each step are identified. Also, any indispensable resource needed for these capabilities is specified. These resources could be skills, facilities, information, technology, etc.

The capabilities are classified by colours:

- Red: capability does not exist and cannot be easily acquired
- Amber: capability exists or can be reached but will need to be developed
- Green: capability exists or can be easily acquired

4.1.4 *How to profit*

This is the final step, which consists of identifying the best pricing strategy to help the business monetise the value it creates, making it viable and able to scale. Additionally, the guide provides some tips for this stage to think about the pricing model and its financial and non-financial effects:

- Selection of the pricing model.
- Benefits of the chosen pricing strategy over other alternatives.
- Establish how to report non-financial value.
- Think about how the chosen pricing strategy benefits the customer.
- Price of the product/service.
- Organisational implications in the business.
- Impact of the pricing strategy on the revenue and costs.

5. Results

The first workshop for value chain definition was engaged on:

- Description of the three value chains (3D b-bTPs foam printing, Bead foaming of b-bTPs, Foam Injection Moulding)
- What can be managed in VITAL project
- Establish the risk and loss of value in the value chains

For this purpose, the first step of the Circular design guide: Where to play was followed, but just the first two parts:

- a) Map existing value flow.
- b) Lost of value and value risk.

The application used in this workshop was Mural [1] which allow to create murals online with various persons at same time. All mural value chains figures are in the appendix (: Mural obtained in the workshop.).

The main conclusions that raised during the meeting are described in the following.

5.1 Foam Injection Moulding (FIM)

5.1.1 Value chain description

The value chain of FIM (

Figure 1) starts with two principal chains: b-TPs manufacturing and moulding creation.

- The b-TPs manufacturing start with the production of organic/inorganic additives and the production and rifting of plastic. Those additives and plastics are used for manufacturing the PLA and Bio-PP (b-TPs).
- The moulding creation needs of two lines of information: characteristic of the b-TPs and the part design to be created. Once the material is selected and the part is defined, the mould is created.

Once the moulding is created and the b-TPs to use is produced, the b-TPs is injected into the moulding with a foaming agent to create the final piece. The piece is sent to be assembly into the vehicle that will be use for the final customer.

At same time, different tests are executed to check the performance of the foaming, characterization of the raw material used, and the performance of the final piece.

5.1.1.1 Managed by VITAL

VITAL can control most of the value chain:

- All the steps on the creation of the moulding are controlled by VITAL.
- The compounding of the b-TPs.
- Masterbatch and non-PLA production.
- Test of performance of foaming, characterization of raw materials, performance of final piece.

5.1.1.2 Not Managed by VITAL.

The manufacturing of organic and inorganic additives, also the production and refining of plastic for b-TPs creation are made outside of VITAL limits. At same time, what happened at end of life of the piece created in VITAL is not managed.

5.1.2 Risks and loss of value

At same that the value chain was defined the partners think about which are the current risk of the project and defined principal risk factors:

- Additives materials can't comply with requirements.
- Geometry redesign may be needed.
- b-bTPs alternatives are not available in required amounts.
- Developed biomaterials are not compatible with current Doblo tool and difficult to assemble prior validations.
- Lack of property recovery in additives.
- Raw material shortages in sourcing.
- Not able to achieve customer demand.
- Regulation problems

In addition, the most important loss of value is there is no definition on how to recycle and obtain the plastic in the end of life of the piece created.

5.2 3D b-bTPs foam printing

5.2.1 Value chain description

Due to the novelty of this process (Figure 2), the first step is the creation of 3D foam head able to produce 3D piece by extrusion through the addition of layer. It's necessary to design and develop a foam head bench, develop a digital twin of the printing head to be able to simulate the effects of parameters in the process, this will accelerate the obtention of the final 3D printing foam head.

Once the head is created, it integrated into a 3D platform. In this integration the optimization of the foam printing process is optimized at same time the bio-based polymer used is optimized for 3D foam printing.

When the process of 3D printing is optimized, this could be scale-up and be ready to be used to produce 3D printing pieces. The design of 3D printed piece needs of:

- Material selection, that depend on the final use of the piece
- Product configurations, that depend on the piece design, and what size is possible to produce
- Start of the element production.
- Element installation
- After the element reach its final life, this element must be recycled, and put it back in the value chain.

5.2.1.1 Managed by VITAL.

3D b-bTPs foam printing is a novelty process that is being developed by VITAL, so all the value chain is under managed of the VITAL project.

5.2.2 Risk and loss of value

The principal risks are:

- Part integrity (layer adhesion, speed surface quality, foam quality, etc.).
- Raw material shortages in sourcing
- The recyclability of the final product is compromised by the material quality or product design
- The post processing of the pieces created by 3D printing might lead to high cost.

The principal loss of value is the possibility to not able to recover the pieces created after end of use.

5.3 Bead foaming of b-bTPs

5.3.1 Value chain description

The value chain starts with selection of the raw materials for the production and optimization of the PLA (Figure 3), and selection and production of Masterbatch and non-PLA compound. Once, all materials are selected this will supply to production of bead foam.

For bead foaming processing is necessary to develop and optimize the bead foam recipes and process for b-bTPs material. Also, the material must be tested to check if reach the needed characteristic of use. The final product will be sent to production.

5.3.1.1 Managed by VITAL.

VITAL can manage most of the value chain:

- Selection and optimization of PLA
- Optimization and development of bean process
- Test and definition of the final bead foam product

5.3.1.2 Not Managed by VITAL.

The supplier of the material to produce the PLA is out of the limits of VITAL, also the final production partner.

5.3.2 Risk and loss of value

The current principal risks of the value chain are:

- Part requirements cannot be met with bead foam system.
- Material not feasible for bread foam process.
- Raw material shortages in sourcing

6. Conclusions

During the workshop, VITAL's partners were able to define all the necessary steps in order to develop and obtain a final defined process, despite of being in the early stages of the project. Furthermore, the partnership identifies that most of all the necessary steps that must be accomplished can be managed within the project.

On the other hand, although each value chain has its own associated risks, there is one risk which is repeated in all: raw material shortage. It is a critical risk that mainly affect to material production, so it must be properly addressed by VITAL for the proper achievement of the objectives. Partners are already studying how to solve this issue and plan to iterate over it during upcoming the workshops.

This document has described the methodology that will be followed in VITAL project for the definition and development of the three value chains. As mentioned above, different workshops will take place in the upcoming Consortium Meetings to iterate over the previous ideas and also to proceed with all the steps defined in the proposed business model plan. In addition, the primary results obtained in the first meeting has been analysed. The final report about the value chain definition, due to M36, will describe the whole process and will compile all the information gathered from the workshops and partners for the final definition of VITAL's value chains.

7. References

- [1] "Mural," [Online]. Available: <https://app.mural.co/>. [Accessed 29 09 2022].
- [2] Ellen Macarthur Foundation, University of Exeter, Paconsulting, "Circular Business Model Design Guide," 2020. [Online]. Available: http://www2.paconsulting.com/rs/526-HZE-833/images/Circular%20Business%20Design%20Guide_10.pdf.

Appendix 1: Mural obtained in the workshop.

Figure 1. Mural obtained for the FIM value chain.

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Figure 3. Mural obtained for the bead foaming of b-BTPs value chain

